

PATHOGENICITY OF *XYLELLA* *FASTIDIOSA* ON PLANTS OF INTEREST FOR FRANCE

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Xylella fastidiosa was detected for the first time outdoor in France in 2015. Since the detection of the first focus in Corsica several sequence types (STs) and subspecies have been identified on nearly 30 plant species. Other STs have been detected in Europe on intercepted coffee plants, in nurseries, and in natural settings. Determining the real threat that this diversity of strains represent for the main plant productions in France is the aim of the pathogenicity tests we launched. However, due to a strict adhesion to the 2008/61/CE directive, pathogenicity tests using this plant pathogen have to be monitored in type S3 confined growth chambers. In consequence only a limited number of individual can be tested, and due to technical constraints a certain degree of uncertainty surrounds these costly tests conducted during six to 18 months. We plan to test the pathogenicity of strains representing the subspecies *fastidiosa*, *sandyi*, *multiplex*, and *pauca* and especially the STs identified so far in Europe. The plant species and genotypes to be tested have been chosen to represent either an economic interest for mainland France or Corsica (grapevine, apple tree, pear tree, citrus, olive tree), or positive control (coffee, oleander and polygala) or indicator plant (tobacco and periwinkle). Monitoring the pathogenicity of *X. fastidiosa* strains is part of our involvement in both H2020 projects POnTE and XF-ACTORS.